

**DIGITALIZATION IN BANKING: FINANCIAL PLANNING AND WEALTH
MANAGEMENT - THE PART BANKS PLAY IN PROSPERITY**

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Abstract

Wealth management and financial planning are increasingly essential and ubiquitous. In order to support banks' presence in this industry, which has enormous growth potential, the authors of this paper have attempted to discuss the growing significance of financial planning and wealth management, the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on these topics, recent trends in financial planning and wealth management, a SWOT analysis of the financial planning and wealth management industry at both the global and Indian levels, the role of banks in financial planning and wealth management, and the growing use of technology by banks in this sector.

Keywords:

Wealth management, financial planning

Examining and Evaluating Financial Planning and Wealth Management

In order to safeguard their financial future, people of all ages must practise wealth management and financial planning. Financial planning entails developing a thorough plan to handle money and reach particular financial objectives. The expert management of a person's assets is referred to as wealth management. Wealth management and financial planning can ease anxiety and lessen stress brought on by uncertain finances. Financial planning and asset management are essential for everyone, regardless of age, to reach their financial objectives and safeguard their financial future. Younger people could be more concerned with building a solid financial foundation, which includes saving for a down payment on a house, budgeting, and student loan repayment. As people get older, they might start concentrating on longer-term objectives including estate preparation, retirement planning, and income-generating investment portfolio management. According to a Research and Markets research, the worldwide wealth management market is expected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 5.3% from 2020 to 2025, reaching \$116.3 billion by that time. India is not exempt from the growing significance of wealth management and financial planning. In addition, a report published by the Indian Wealth Management Industry Association (IWMI) projects that the country's wealth management market would expand at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 15.7% between 2020 and 2025, when it is estimated to reach INR 8.5 trillion (\$117 billion). Growth drivers identified by the research include the emergence of digital wealth management platforms, rising disposable incomes, and an increase in the number of high net worth individuals.

Covid-19's Impact on Wealth Management and Financial Planning

The COVID-19 epidemic has had a major effect on the financial planning and asset management business. The pandemic's effects on economic instability and market volatility have forced the sector to adapt in a number of ways. It is noteworthy to mention the following:

Growth in demand for wealth management and financial planning services: As a result of the pandemic's uncertainty, a lot of investors have looked for these services to help them make wise investment choices and navigate the erratic markets. According to a survey conducted by the consulting firm EY, during the pandemic, 64% of investors used asset management and financial planning services more frequently.

Transition to digital platforms: The financial planning and wealth management industries have seen a transition to digital platforms as a result of the pandemic compelling many businesses to go online. Digital tools and online resources have become indispensable for wealth managers and financial advisors in their daily interactions with clients on investment management.

Growth in sustainable investing: As a result of the pandemic, which has re-emphasized sustainability and social responsibility, investors are now more eager to fund companies that are positively impacting society and the environment. A survey by the consulting firm Morgan Stanley indicates that 64% of investors are thinking about making sustainable investments.

Increased use of Robo-advisory services: As more investors look for affordable and effective solutions to manage their finances, the pandemic has raised interest in robo-advisory services. According to a report by A.T. Kearney, a consulting firm, by 2025, the global assets under management (AUM) of robo-advisors is projected to reach \$3 trillion.

Growth in online financial education: As a result of the epidemic, more people are spending time managing their finances, which has led to a growth in online financial tools and education. A lot of wealth managers and financial advisors have begun educating their clients about financial planning and asset management through online resources like webinars.

Overall, the COVID-19 pandemic has had a major effect on the asset management and financial planning sectors. Due to the market volatility and economic volatility brought on by the pandemic, there is a greater need for wealth management and financial planning services. Additionally, there is a shift in focus towards digital platforms, a rise in the usage of robo-advisory services, and an increase in online financial education.

Current Developments in Wealth Management and Financial Planning

The financial planning and wealth management sector is expanding, with the following emerging as key trends in the field:

Sustainability and Impact Investing: In recent years, there has been a growing emphasis on sustainable and socially responsible investing as more investors want to align their investments with their beliefs and have a positive impact on the environment and society.

Automation and Digitization: As a result of technological advancements, the financial planning and wealth management sectors have experienced an automation and digitization shift. The usage of algorithms by robo-advisory services, which provide automated portfolio management and financial advice, has increased recently.

Environmental, social, and governance (ESG) investing is becoming more and more popular since it is thought to be a means of achieving higher profits while still being consistent with the ethical ideals of the investors. Research from the Global Sustainable Investment Alliance projects that \$30.7 trillion in ESG assets will be managed by 2020.

Behavioural Finance: In the fields of wealth management and financial planning, behavioural finance has grown in importance. It is the study of how psychological factors influence one's ability to make financial decisions. Behavioural finance is being used by a large number of wealth managers and financial advisors to better understand their clients' emotions and biases and to offer more individualised and practical financial planning guidance.

In general, digitalization and automation, ESG investment, behavioural finance, sustainability and impact investing, and digitalization and automation are the most recent trends in financial planning and wealth management on a global scale. Financial advisers and wealth managers can better serve their customers and assist them in reaching their financial objectives by being aware of and responsive to these developments.

SWOT Analysis of the Financial Planning and Wealth Management Industries in India and Globally

To be an excellent player in any sector, one must have a thorough understanding of the possibilities, threats, and industry strengths and limitations. The writers of this work have conducted a SWOT analysis of the Indian and worldwide financial planning and wealth management industries. In conclusion, the SWOT analysis of the global and Indian financial planning and wealth management

industries reveals that, despite upcoming problems, there is a great deal of opportunity for industry participants to generate sizable revenue and profits.

Banks' Part in Wealth Management and Financial Planning

In India, banks are crucial to wealth management and financial planning. Savings accounts, fixed deposits, mutual funds, insurance, and wealth management services are just a few of the many financial goods and services that banks provide. In India, banks usually provide wealth management services via their wealth management or private banking departments. Tax planning, financial guidance and portfolio management are a few examples of these services. For high net worth individuals, banks may additionally provide specialised wealth management services including trust administration and inheritance planning. To meet the rising demand for wealth management services in the nation, several Indian banks have recently concentrated on boosting their offerings. Additionally, banks are using technology to improve the wealth management services they offer. Examples of this include using robo-advisory services, digital platforms, and other analytical tools to deliver more effective and individualized care. Banks also offer a large range of financial products, such as bonds, mutual funds, and other fixed-income securities. Banks offer insurance services such as life, health, and general insurance to safeguard the futures of its consumers.

Furthermore, Indian banks offer a wide range of financial planning services, including estate, retirement, and tax planning. These services can help clients organise their finances and make sure they have enough cash on hand to meet their long-term goals. In summary, Indian banks are essential to financial planning and asset management because they offer a broad range of financial products and services to their customers, including mutual funds, savings accounts, term deposits, insurance, and wealth management services. Due to increased competition among banks and growing demand for wealth management services, many Indian banks have recently focused on developing and expanding their wealth management offerings. According to a report by the consulting firm KPMG, the Indian wealth management market is expected to develop at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 15% and reach \$2 trillion by 2025. According to the report, India will have 4.5 million High Net worth Individuals by 2025, with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 10%.

All of this suggests that insurance is becoming a more vital instrument for financial planning in India. In conclusion, the rising number of HNWIs in the nation is predicted to propel the wealth management market in India, which is projected to rise at a 15% CAGR and reach \$2 trillion by 2025. With the share of bank-managed assets in the wealth management market predicted to rise from 35% in 2018 to 45% in 2023, banks are anticipated to play a major role in this market.

Banks' Increasing Use of Technology for Wealth Management and Financial Planning

Financial planning and wealth management services are increasingly being offered by banks in India and throughout the world through the use of technology.

Here are some examples

In Singapore, DBS Bank introduced NAV Planner, an AI-powered financial planning tool that assists clients in organising their assets and money according to their risk tolerance and personal objectives. With over 300,000 users since its 2019 launch, NAV Planner has greatly aided DBS in growing its assets under management.

In India, HDFC Bank has introduced HDFC MF Online, a robo-advisory platform that leverages machine learning algorithms to deliver clients personalised investment advice. With more than 2.5 million registered customers, the platform has significantly increased HDFC Bank's assets under management.

JP Morgan has introduced the You Invest app in the US. It offers users customised investing advice depending on their risk tolerance and financial objectives. With more than two million users, the app has considerably increased JP Morgan's assets under management.

In India, ICICI Bank has introduced iPal, a voice-activated virtual assistant that can give users details about their investment portfolios, transactions, and account balances. The assistant interprets

client inquiries and responds with a customised message using machine learning techniques and natural language processing.

These are only a handful of the ways that banks are using technology to take advantage of the enormous potential that the financial planning and wealth management industries are delivering. This appears to be just the beginning, as 77% of banks worldwide, according to a World Economic Forum poll, intend to invest in artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning technology for wealth management services within the next two years. Additionally, according to the poll, 53% of banks intend to invest in distributed ledger and blockchain technology for wealth management. The use of AI and analytics by banks has resulted in improved operations and customer service overall. These improvements include personalised customer care, risk management, fraud detection and prevention, credit scoring, and predictive maintenance, all of which have a positive impact on financial planning and wealth management.

Conclusion

It is reasonable to say that one of the sectors with the fastest growth, both nationally and internationally, is financial planning and wealth management. The main factors propelling the industry's expansion include rising disposable income, the number of high net worth individuals, and the emergence of digital wealth management platforms. The covid pandemic has had a beneficial effect on the sector because of the rise in demand for wealth management and financial planning services brought on by the pandemic's economic uncertainty and market volatility. ESG investment, digitalization and automation, sustainability and impact investing, and behavioural finance are the most recent developments in financial planning and wealth management on a worldwide scale. Financial advisers and wealth managers can better serve their customers and assist them in reaching their financial objectives by being aware of and responsive to these developments. One of the key pillars of the economy is the bank, and both the bank and the client benefit from their presence in the financial planning and wealth management sectors. To meet the rising demand for wealth management services in the nation, several Indian banks have recently concentrated on boosting their offerings. Additionally, banks are using technology to improve the wealth management services they offer. Examples of this include using robo-advisory services, digital platforms, and other analytical tools to deliver more effective and individualised care. Thus, it seems sense to conclude that the existence of banks as important service providers will make the financial planning and wealth management sector better, more stable, more dynamic.

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